

CREATIVE
INFORMATICS

Understanding Membership Data in the Creative Industries: The Creative Edinburgh Data Project

A Creative Informatics Report

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Executive Summary

In October 2023, the teams of [Creative Edinburgh](#) and [Creative Informatics](#) joined forces to spearhead an innovative project exploring the power of data for the creative sector, called [Creative Edinburgh & Creative Informatics Data Project](#). The overall goal of this innovative project was threefold: (1) to conduct a case study project into exploring the power of data for the creative sector, specifically for Creative Edinburgh (CE); (2) to develop concrete recommendations for CE how to improve their existing data collection and membership database approach; and (3) to showcase this project as a potential template for other creative sector organizations regarding the deployment of an ethical and diversity-embracing approach to using data as a powerful tool for the creative industries sector.

The main recommendations can be summarised under the key-terms ***User-Centricity***, ***ED&I*** and ***Data-Circularity***:

User-Centricity Recommendations:

1. Work with relevant stakeholders of the community to gain first-hand understanding of the kind of data that is needed – develop the main questions that the community aims to answer through their data collection initiative
2. Adapt the overall data collection plan to the actual economic setting of those that will be responsible for the data collection and analysis – check their personnel availability, expertise, etc
3. Always follow the mandate ‘quality over quantity’ – triple-check each question on the survey whether it is really necessary or not.

ED&I Recommendations:

4. Make sure the overall survey follows ED&I considerations, be mindful of how minorities who historically have been overlooked might perceive questions that reflect a standardised Western world view.

5. Make sure to show how members can entirely delete or change the information they provided. Be very transparent and clear which information that is provided will be displayed publicly, anonymized or not, and which stays private/within the data collecting organization.
6. Be very sure about the purpose and reason for asking questions/collecting data. This communicates a peer-level, where those that provide information feel like they are in control of the whole data collection process (also part of the data circularity principle).

Data-Circularity Recommendations:

7. Work with stakeholders that could function as broadcasters in the community and can help to increase support and data provision
8. Check what formal data collection/surveying structures are already in place from government organizations and find out how data-circularity could work in both ways. Make sure to use similar or matching variables/categories
9. Look out for other examples of existing data collection approaches – learn from best practice.
10. Make sure data collection follows a logical flow that mirrors how people typically provide information.
11. Consider relevant cross-tabulation approaches for the analysis, check which variables would be useful to pair with other variables.
12. Offer different levels of personal information questions, reflecting different membership tiers that demand different levels of commitment. Members should feel in that they get something back for providing more information.

1 Introduction

The *Creative Edinburgh & Creative Informatics Data Project* started in October 2023, with colleagues from the University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University as well as Creative Edinburgh jointly defining a project brief and milestones with an envisaged project end by the end of March 2024¹. Both teams had been collaborating since 2018 in the AHRC funded Cluster [Creative Informatics](#); and the project was also an outcome of prior research conducted by colleagues in the Creative Informatics project regarding the relevance of data and data mapping for the creative industries sector in Scotland and beyond (Panneels et al., 2021). The project's main outcome was aimed to be this report with best-practice recommendations for the creative industries landscape in Scotland regarding data use, data collection and data circularity, with a focus on ethics, and equality, diversity and inclusion (ED&I). We now present this final report as a concerted effort, encompassing several deliverables and work aspects of this project. We present the project background and context, a Creative Edinburgh-specific depiction of their data-collection efforts over the past years, recommendations and suggestions as to how to continue these efforts, and concluding remarks.

Foregoing were other deliverables, such as a first report on our initial analysis and understanding of CE's data collection approach, a presentation to relevant stakeholders (e.g., Scottish Government representatives, SOSE and Creative Scotland) and numerous meetings with Creative Edinburgh colleagues discussing their data needs and their approach. It should be emphasised that Creative Edinburgh can be seen as a front runner in terms of their engagement and understanding regarding the importance of a robust data collection approach, including a membership management system to effectively serve its growing and diverse community. Over time, their data collection needs have evolved, necessitating a continuous evaluation of available platforms.

¹ The project end was defined by the end of the funding term for the Creative Informatics project.

CE's journey began a decade ago with exploring readily available options like Google Forms. While these solutions offered basic functionality, they ultimately lacked the features necessary for managing a complex membership structure and capturing the depth of data required for meaningful insights. In search of a more comprehensive solution, Creative Edinburgh transitioned to platforms like [Wild Apricot](#). These membership management tools provided a significant improvement, offering features for member communication, event management, and streamlined data collection. Today, Creative Edinburgh utilises [Join It](#), a platform specifically designed for membership management. Join It offers the functionality and flexibility required to meet their current needs, enabling them to effectively collect, manage, and utilise data to support their members.

Following, we will introduce Creative Edinburgh's data collection approach first on a high-level discussing the platform and its functionalities and how they correspond to CE's needs. In a second step, we discuss the actual data collection tool – the survey providing the data input for their membership database – and specifications. We then will be introducing suggested amendments and changes. Finally, we present an overview with recommendations for robust data collection practices, which will be of value to the creative sector and, more specifically, to other creative membership organisations.

1.1 Methodology

Our overall methodology followed a case study approach for which we employed a living lab framework. Living labs are described as experimentation in a real world setting and emphasize a non-hierarchical research structure. They name research subjects as users who participate in co-creating products, services, or spaces (Almirall et al., 2012; see also Femenías & Hagbert, 2013). Living labs are often interdisciplinary projects that can involve everyday citizens (users), industry players, the public sector, and academics (who are generally seen as project facilitators) (Juujärvi and Pessa, 2013). The living labs framework we chose for this project integrates methods and instruments based on co-design aiming to create an inclusive and ethical framework to investigate the needs of the

creative industries sector and to better understand how data collection or data-mapping can work for creative practitioners and communities.

The academic team, consisting of researchers from University of Edinburgh and Edinburgh Napier University, started working with colleagues from Creative Edinburgh (CE) by meeting to discuss their understanding of data, its relevance for their organization, challenges, and benefits. There were also meetings to discuss CE's level of data-literacy, i.e. practical data collection and analysis expertise, as well as their staff resources overall. Given CE is a small, not-for-profit organisation, there was no large budget that they could easily spend on additional training and work time for their staff. This is reflective of the creative and cultural sector at large and as such an important consideration. Overall, together we came up with a summary of CE's specific data goals, existing expertise, and economic/personnel related infrastructure.

The integral co-creation element was executed through regular meetings and on-site discussions with different team members from CE regarding their needs and expectations for a practical data collection and analysis environment. One of the first steps was to formulate the key questions that CE wanted to answer, and which they hoped could be addressed through analysis of data collected from members. The academic team subsequently developed a first set of suggestions for new and altered questions, and we discussed these in the main team regarding feasibility. This is also called an iterative approach, loosely taken from the iterative interaction design method (Preece, Rogers, & Sharp, 2023), where a new design is iteratively tested, refined and again tested with the relevant end-users to integrate their specific design needs.

The final step in this case study was to present this report incorporating the recommendations and a narrative regarding the journey towards these recommendations, as well as producing additional dissemination material. It is planned to add workshops with practitioners to discuss these recommendations and further refine our results and overall methodology.

2 Creative Edinburgh's Platform Specifications

Creative Edinburgh's need and use of digital platforms, software packages, which facilitate the management of their membership data, has evolved over the years as their membership has grown and demands have changed. Join It – the platform currently used by CE – aims to streamline membership management for organisations of all sizes with a suite of user-friendly features. Notable features in CE's usage context include:

2.1 Membership tiers

The tiers feature caters to a diverse audience. This flexibility helps to create a structure that reflects the varying needs and interests of the members and potentially incentivises increased engagement. Members are motivated to move up the tiers by enjoying escalating benefits with each tier. For instance, CE uses Join It's tiered memberships to effectively reach a broader audience. Their "Premium" tier (a higher paid for membership level) exemplifies this perfectly, offering access to free and discounted co-working spaces at select partner venues, catering to freelancers and professionals seeking a collaborative work environment. This benefit provides a clear value proposition for those who require flexible workspace solutions. This functionality allows potential members to select the option that best aligns with their needs and aspirations. When members sign up, data is collected.

2.2 Member data collection

The platform offers a flexible membership management system through a combination of default questions and customisable fields.

Default Questions: Every membership tier comes pre-loaded with a set of essential information fields commonly required by most organisations. These include basic contact details like names, email addresses, and social media handles. This streamlines the process for organisations by providing a foundation of member information.

Custom Fields (Paid Packages): This feature is available only for organisations subscribed to paid Join It packages allowing for the creation of unique data points specific to an organisation's requirements. A diverse range of field types are offered, including text boxes, paragraph boxes, radio buttons, dropdown menus, checkboxes, and waivers. This flexibility ensures organisations can gather the precise information needed from their members. For example, CE gains valuable insights into their membership using “custom fields” as shown in the table below as opposed to relying only upon default fields offered by the Join It platform.

Table 1: Examples of Join It’s default questions and Creative Edinburgh’s customised questions

DEFAULT JOIN IT QUESTIONS
First Name
Last Name
Email
EXAMPLES OF CREATIVE EDINBURGH'S CUSTOMISED QUESTIONS
Why have you chosen to join Creative Edinburgh? ²
Postcode
Which sector of the Creative Industries do you primarily work in?
Which status do you primarily identify with currently?
About - Tell us a little about yourself & what you do

2.3 Membership data import

Join It offers a streamlined import process to add members and their corresponding information into the membership database. This enables CE to then be able to apply queries to its data and gain insights into the cumulated data. To achieve this, Join It generates an organisation specific import template that can be downloaded. This

² Only question that is not requiring any input.

template incorporates both platform default fields and any custom fields established within the organisations' account, ensuring a comprehensive data import experience.

2.4 Data reporting and export

Join It gives granular control over member data exports. This means it allows for tailored data management by enabling selective member field exports, ensuring retrieval of only specific information for different queries. For instance, one might just need basic contact information like email addresses for a mailing campaign. Or, perhaps it may require a more in-depth export that includes creative sector data, employment status or postcode data for geographical mapping. The platform requires an administrator to select the fields that are relevant for a particular query. After choosing the desired fields, a simple click on the "Export Report" button initiates the download process. It then prepares the data and makes it available for download.

Utilisation of this feature ensures export of data necessary for analysis while upholding strong data privacy practices. By only extracting the specific fields required for analysis, this feature helps to reduce the amount of downloaded data containing potentially sensitive information. Ensuring that the subscriber knows that their data will only be viewed by an authorised data analyst or data controller is key in creating trust between members and organisations. Having insight of why their data might be used, and oversight as to what data subscribers have control over is critical. By excluding personal identifiers like names or postcodes, the organisation can focus on trends without compromising individual privacy. Moreover, by not downloading the entire database, there is less data at risk if a security breach were to occur. Therefore, asking questions such as, "what is the purpose" of downloading such data is always a good start.

2.5 Event management

CE leverages Join It's powerful integration with [Eventbrite](#), a leading event management platform, to streamline event management and member engagement. Features under this include real-time syncing that ensures both platforms have the most up-to-date member information. This eliminates the need for manual data entry and ensures discounts and access codes are always applied correctly. Organisations can create customised benefits

for different membership tiers. This might involve offering member-only discounts or early access to event tickets. Moreover, Eventbrite orders and check-ins are automatically recorded within Join It's dashboard, linked to the specific member. This provides valuable data on member engagement and participation in events. CE, for example, analyses RSVPs and attendance rates to understand which events resonate most with their members. Additionally, the integration identifies non-member attendees, allowing CE to follow up and potentially convert them into new members.

2.6 Emails and newsletters

CE utilises the partnership of Join It and [MailChimp](#), a popular email marketing platform. The membership database is always up to date within the chosen email marketing tool, eliminating the need for manual updates and potential discrepancies. For example, Creative Edinburgh integrates their Join It with MailChimp to manage their email newsletters. Join It ensures their entire member database is consistently synced with MailChimp, allowing them to segment their audience and send targeted newsletters based on member interests or membership types. Mailchimp also gives them, like Eventbrite, detailed analysis and insights into their members engagements with the content (e.g opening rate, clicks, etc).

3 Creative Edinburgh's Membership Survey

Creative Edinburgh's membership data structure lays a solid foundation for understanding their community. It captures core, required information (name, contact details) alongside valuable insights like creative sector and member motivations for joining. The membership sign-up process involves creating a profile on the "Join IT" hosted web page. This profile serves as an online directory listing for potential creative individuals and others. In particular, the membership database includes mandatory fields, denoted by an asterisk, emphasising key information for building comprehensive member profiles (see Table 2 below). This information is collected by Creative Edinburgh for its internal use, reporting duties and data analysis purposes.

Additional non-compulsory questions serve as an incentive for members, enhancing the depth of their online profiles in the context of their Membership Directory by allowing optional information such as phone number, profile photo, website and social media links to be collected, demonstrating a commitment to inclusivity by offering optional Equality, Diversity & Inclusion (ED&I) questions for self-identification. Creative Edinburgh is giving its members control over which data its members want to share publicly with other members. The organisation has further taken proactive steps to enhance data accuracy, particularly in the sector categories, which are now collected with greater precision through a set of 16 sectors aligned with the 16 [Scottish Creative and Cultural Industries](#). This shift is aligned with the organisation's commitment to providing a more comprehensive and inclusive representation of the creative community. Despite historical data inconsistency challenges arising due to shifting and evolving data collection processes over the years, Creative Edinburgh's commitment to evolve its data collection methodology reflects its dedication to serving and supporting its diverse membership base.

Table 2: Creative Edinburgh’s Membership Survey (Current Status)

CURRENT SURVEY QUESTIONS	CRITERIA
First Name and Last Name*	Required
Email*	Required
Date of Birth*	Required
Phone	Optional
Profile Photo	Optional
Business Name (if applicable)	Optional
Website	Optional
Instagram	Optional
Facebook	Optional
Twitter	Optional
LinkedIn	Optional
YouTube	Optional
TikTok	Optional
Why have you chosen to join Creative Edinburgh?	Optional
Postcode*	Required
Which sector of the Creative Industries do you primarily work in? * Advertising and Marketing AI, Software Development and Website Design Architecture Arts Education and Research Crafts and Traditional Arts Creative Practitioner Culture, Communities and Heritage Design (Exhibition, Fashion, Game, Graphic and Product) Festivals Film, social media, TV, Radio and Other Media Literature and Publishing Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy Museums, Galleries and Libraries Performing Arts (Comedy, Dance, Music, Opera, Theatre) Visual Arts and Curatorial Services	Required
Which status do you primarily identify with currently? * Company/Organisation	Required

Employed Self Employed Student Unemployed Retired	
About - Tell us a little about yourself & what you do*	Required

After completing the sign-up process, an incentive for completing the optional information is displayed as part of terms and conditions, which currently says the following³: “The information you have shared here will be displayed in our members library. Please check your contact information and leave blank any methods you do not wish to be contacted by.” Providing more details strengthens member’s online profile within the Creative Edinburgh Membership Directory. This directory is accessible to individuals and organisations seeking freelancers and small businesses, increasing visibility and potential for collaboration or commission.

Additional optional questions related to ED&I are asked in the first email upon signing up. Members are given the opportunity to respond to these questions anonymously. They include gender, age, sexuality, nationality, disability. Completing the ED&I data points helps CE understand the makeup of their membership and potentially inform future initiatives focused on inclusivity within the organisation. However, its rationale needs to be communicated clearly and is a key feature of the three principles of user centricity, ED&I and data circularity.

³ <https://creative-edinburgh.com/members-library/>

4 Towards futureproofing data requirements

Creative Edinburgh's membership is a vibrant tapestry, constantly growing and diversifying. This flourishing community directly translates into evolving data collection needs. However, this is not just about managing member information, it is also about wielding data as a powerful tool for creative industries' advocacy. In this section, evolving data collection strategy requirements are emphasised to support Creative Edinburgh's advocacy efforts.

4.1 Streamlining the flow

Creative Edinburgh's current membership data collection offers valuable insights into their community. At present, the form collects personal details like name, email, and date of birth sequentially, which is a good starting point. However, there is an opportunity to optimise the placement of other details like postcode for a smoother user experience. Geographical data might help small businesses find collaborators or partners, which is a key feature for creative SMEs and freelancers (see Panneels et al, 2024) or help clients find businesses.

The data collection should follow a logical flow that mirrors how people typically provide information. For instance, postcode is often associated with address details, which could be captured later but in the same personal details section. Another example being, "why have you chosen to join Creative Edinburgh?" - this question currently appears towards the end of the form. However, capturing this information earlier in the process could be more beneficial. Understanding a member's motivations right after they provide basic contact details allows Creative Edinburgh to tailor the remaining data collection to those specific needs as for users to easily find what they need, the navigation elements across similar pages and sections should have a consistent layout and clear labels (Nielsen & Loranger, 2006).

The data collection form should follow a logical flow that mirrors the order people typically provide information. For instance, "postcode", which currently appears late in the form in the social media/business information section, is more typically requested as part of personal details (partly because it is often captured alongside address), but this grouping also appears more logical because postcodes are sufficiently accurate that they can be highly personally identifiable.

4.2 Differentiated data collection for different membership tiers

While Join It offers the flexibility of creating tiered forms for different membership levels, implementing this approach for CE requires careful consideration. Tailored forms for paid memberships could capture richer data from highly engaged members. However, this benefit comes with the potential drawback of creating separate data sets for each tier. Analysing data across these fragmented sets can become cumbersome. Currently, the vast majority (approximately 6,240) of Creative Edinburgh's members belong to the core or unpaid tier. With only 57 paid members, the resources required to manage separate forms and data sets might not be justified at this point. Given their current membership makeup, a well-structured, single form might be the most practical solution. However, Join It's conditional logic feature can be leveraged to achieve some level of granularity. By incorporating conditional logic, Creative Edinburgh can display additional, relevant questions only to paid members upon selecting their membership tier or from members they need more information from. This approach allows them to gather more in-depth information from their most engaged segment without the complexities of separate databases.

4.3 Improving understanding of motivations to join

The membership survey could be optimised to enable better understanding of a member's motivations for joining, and how they heard about Creative Edinburgh. The current question set provides qualitative data from free text fields, however, data could be more readily analysed and acted upon if the questions were modified to provide a structured quantitative picture of the responses. This could be achieved by, for example, rephrasing the existing " Why have you chosen to join Creative Edinburgh?" question to incorporate

a sub-question about discovery. This may include, for example, "Why are you joining Creative Edinburgh?" and offering a list of common reasons to join, such as networking, resources, etc. with a checkbox for "Other" and a text field to elaborate. The inclusion of a separate question, "Where did you hear about us?" with options like "Website," "Social Media," "Referral," and "Other" with a text field, could yield insightful data to support more impactful marketing strategies.

4.4 Public – Private delineation

Creative Edinburgh's membership data collection process provides valued understandings of their vibrant community. While transparency is an essential cornerstone of effective data collection, Creative Edinburgh does not explicitly distinguish between public and private information. This lack of clarity can lead to confusion and potentially unwanted information being displayed publicly. Furthermore, unintentional oversharing may happen where members might unknowingly share sensitive information they intended to keep private, leading to privacy concerns and potentially compromising their professional or personal lives. Moreover, confusion surrounding data usage could erode members' trust in Creative Edinburgh's data collection practices. This could discourage valuable information being gathered and hinder the organisation's ability to understand the needs of their community. Thus, there is an opportunity to enhance transparency around data privacy and empowering members to control their information. Articulating the purpose of the data collection, Creative Edinburgh could explain why they collect specific data, for example to advocate for the creative community and to develop targeted support programs. It might also be helpful to highlight how data contributes to broader industry understanding, benefiting the entire creative sector in Scotland. Whilst Creative Edinburgh could clarify which data is held privately (e.g., for use in industry representation) and which is shared publicly within the member database, there would also be benefit articulating the benefit of sharing some data publicly. For instance, Creative Edinburgh could emphasise how interested parties such as potential collaborators, clients or employers might discover and connect with creatives might be an 'acceptable' trade-off for the data collection by Creative Edinburgh: ***articulating this 'data circularity' is thus critical.***

On the practical and implementing side of the survey, Join It does not offer visual cues like icons or colours, for clear demarcation of, e.g., public and private fields. A creative solution lies within the existing Terms & Conditions (T&C) text. The current form structure places a crucial statement regarding publicly displayed information at the very end, before a link to Creative Edinburgh's full T&C and privacy policy. This placement significantly increases the likelihood of members overlooking such critical information. This challenge can be addressed by repurposing the statement and extracting the relevant portion of the T&C that mentions the member library display and contact preferences, and rewriting the extracted text in a clear, concise, and easily understandable way. Placing this repurposed text prominently at the very beginning of the membership form, before any data collection fields will highlight the privacy choices. Bold or underlining key phrases like "public profile information" and "contact information for internal use only" to draw attention to the data distinction is one way to do it. By placing this information at the beginning of the form, members see it before they start sharing any data. This upfront communication empowers members to make informed choices about what they share publicly and what they prefer to keep private.

As an example, repurposed text may look like "Important note: The information you share here will be displayed in our public member directory. This may include details like your name, social media handles, and website. For internal communication purposes only, we will use your contact information (phone number, email). Please review your contact details and leave blank any methods you don't wish to be contacted by."

4.5 Data deletion and members' right to be forgotten

Complying with UK Data Protection Act⁴ and GDPR⁵ requirements, particularly the guidelines around 'the right to be forgotten'⁶, is integral for any organisation or person aiming to collect data related to people. While this report focuses on the data science side, it is important to point out that Data Protection and GDPR are fundamental to

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/data-protection>

⁵ <https://gdpr.eu/>

⁶ <https://gdpr.eu/right-to-be-forgotten/>

consent, trust and data practices. Moreover, any data practice approach comes with legal requirements that must be followed to avoid the risk of fines and legal ramifications. Overall, we recommend CE to work closely with an expert in this field, aiming to streamline the implementation of the Data Protection Law and GDPR, which includes publishing the process so that individuals can make requests⁷.

The current approach for a member's right to have their data deleted is stated within their T&Cs (Section 1.9), which might not be the most conspicuous place for users to find information about deleting their data. As such, there is scope for further clarity and alignment with potential user expectations. The current process requires cancelling the membership followed by a separate email request. This can be cumbersome and confusing for users seeking data deletion and is not clear if partial data can be deleted or amended.

Creating a separate, easily accessible section within the T&Cs or privacy policy specifically explaining and outlining the deletion process is required to ensure Creative Edinburgh are complying with Data Protection best practices. Besides mentioning the deletion process at the sign-up stage, a dedicated form for data deletion requests could lead to better data practice. Also, clearly explaining how long data is typically retained after a deletion request is received is currently not highlighted in the privacy policy. Communicating this clearly is good practice and will ensure that Creative Edinburgh is adhering to relevant regulations and avoiding any potential legal issues. Lastly, providing users with confirmation once their data deletion request is processed is also good data practice.

4.6 Key demographics

Creative Edinburgh has a strong incentive to collect demographic data of its members, but it is crucial to do so transparently and responsibly. The organisation has the

⁷ We also recommend Creative Informatic's publications on this topic, e.g., the Creative Informatics Ethics Statement, <https://zenodo.org/records/3610105> (Osborne, et al., 2020) and the Creative Informatics Research Ethics Overview, <https://zenodo.org/records/3967216> (Elsden et al., 2020).

opportunity to understand trends and patterns within the creative community through data analysis without identifying individual members. By collecting and using demographic data ethically, Creative Edinburgh can gain valuable cognisance while maintaining members' trust. Following are three key demographics that could bring out richer data and research insights: gender, income and geographical data (postcode).

4.6.1 Gender

The absence of a specific emphasis on collecting gender information in membership forms over the years is attributed to a deliberate effort to create an inclusive and welcoming environment for individuals who may prefer not to disclose their gender. However, gender data is valuable for strategic decision-making. Women make up around a third of the creative workforce (and 60% of part-time positions) (National Advisory Council on Women and Girls, 2021), therefore understanding gender makeup is crucial for promoting diversity and inclusivity. Without this information, Creative Edinburgh and policymakers may encounter challenges in developing targeted programs, policies, and initiatives that promote gender diversity and inclusivity.

Introducing "gender" as an optional field with a spectrum of options beyond male/female allows individuals to identify with a specific gender, by choosing "prefer not to disclose," or selecting a term that best reflects their identity. Even with an optional field, some members may choose to share their gender, providing valuable data. Additionally, focusing on broader diversity of data offers a more holistic picture. By combining optional gender data, broader diversity data, and external research and analysis, Creative Edinburgh and external stakeholders can make informed decisions regarding targeted programs and initiatives.

4.6.2 Income

Creative Edinburgh's commitment to its creative members is evident. However, a gap exists in their data collection regarding member income, which is not asked currently. This limits their understanding of the economic landscape within the creative sector in Edinburgh and beyond. By implementing a sensitive and transparent approach to collecting income data, Creative Edinburgh can bridge the current information gap.

Without information on member incomes, Creative Edinburgh only has reduced means to understand the financial realities of their creative community. Without income data, it is difficult to assess the economic well-being of creatives and their sectors, identify potential financial disparities, and advocate for better support mechanisms. For example, the Scottish Government's Growth Sector briefing highlights a lower median income for the creative sector compared to the Scottish average as it states that median weekly full-time earnings across the Scottish Creative Industries growth sector stood at £689.9 in 2023, which was lower than the Scottish average at £702.8 (Scottish Government, 2024). Understanding income distribution within their membership could provide valuable insights to support this sector in both short term (e.g. impact of Covid19 on income) as well as longitudinal studies (e.g. income trends over a five or ten-year period). Creative Edinburgh's diverse membership, encompassing various creative disciplines, could offer a unique perspective on income distribution across different creative sectors. This type of data could be invaluable for advocacy efforts, enabling Creative Edinburgh to tailor arguments and highlight the specific financial challenges faced by different creative professionals in Scotland.

Creative Edinburgh understands that income data can be a personal matter, therefore, the suggestion is to make income reporting entirely optional. It should also be communicated clearly that individual income details will not be shared and how the information will be used -- anonymously and in aggregate form -- to understand the broader economic landscape. Additionally, instead of asking for specific income figures, providing options like income ranges e.g., £25,000 to £35,000 (equivalent to a day rate of approximately £100-£150) etc⁸. also protects individual privacy while offering insights into overall income trends. This ensures members feel comfortable with the data collection process and are more likely to participate if they choose to do so. This approach also avoids any pressure to share sensitive financial information.

⁸ We recommend to map income brackets to either income tax bands (<https://www.mygov.scot/income-tax-rates-and-personal-allowances>), or to include day rates (e.g., mapping to Scottish Artists Union Day Rates, https://www.artistsunion.scot/rates_of_pay_2024).

Insights from income data can additionally be used for benchmarking against national or regional averages, facilitating collaboration with other creative organisations to address broader economic challenges apart from development of targeted resources and programs that address the specific needs of different income brackets within the creative community.

Analysing this information also in connection with other variables, such as gender, can then generate even more powerful and highly relevant insights. Here is a **hypothetical example** to explore the correlation between the representation of female and minority genders members and their income brackets.

- 1. Years (X): the progression of years from 2018 to 2023.
- 2. Percentage of female and minority genders members in the creative sector (Y1): the percentage of female members within a particular creative sector.
- 3. Income brackets (Y2): different income brackets for female members.

Table 3: A hypothetical example to explore the correlation between female and minority genders members’ representation in the creative sector and their income brackets over the years.

Year	% Female and Minority Genders Members in Creative Sector (Y1)	Income Brackets (Y2)
2020	45%	Medium
2021	50%	High
2022	55%	High
2023	50%	Medium

The hypothesis is to understand if there is a correlation between the percentage of females in a specific creative sector and their income brackets over the years. Data

analysis reveals a correlation coefficient (r) is calculated between Y1 and Y2 for each year. Positive correlation would suggest that as the percentage of female and minority genders members in the creative sector increases, there is a trend in income brackets. Different income brackets and sectors could be analysed separately to identify any patterns. The analysis would reveal the strength and direction of the correlation between the percentage of female and minority genders members in the creative sector and their income brackets over the years. This information could guide initiatives aimed at improving income equality and representation within specific income brackets for female and minority genders creatives.

4.6.3 Geographical data

Creative Edinburgh collects postcodes as mandatory information from members, but there is an opportunity to unlock its full potential and enhance the member experience. Currently, the specific benefits of sharing this data are not entirely clear. For a transparent and privacy-centric approach to postcode data collection, Creative Edinburgh could develop a more tailored, regionally focussed and member-centric experience:

Members are not fully aware of how their postcode information is being used and how it benefits them. This lack of transparency can lead to confusion and hesitation to share this data. Moreover, for freelancers and remote workers, full postcode information might raise privacy concerns. Clearly communicating the reasons for collecting postcode data and how it is used anonymously and in aggregate form is recommended. By emphasising that through the implementation of a postcode strategy that asks for the first three characters (e.g., "EH8") as a mandatory field, individual details remain confidential. This allows geographical mapping of creatives while protecting individual privacy. Another crucial point is to consider including an additional layer asking if members are based outside of the UK. This allows those without a UK postcode to participate, too, as without adding a compulsory postcode a potential member cannot currently finish the survey.

In cases of members giving full postcode data, Creative Edinburgh can offer more personalised experiences such as localised events, resources, or networking opportunities relevant to specific regions. Members can also gain access to valuable data

about trends and dynamics within the creative sector in their specific regional areas. This promotes a deeper understanding of the local creative landscape and an added benefit for members. It is also worth noting that networking is a key feature of the “network model of governance” that creatives operate under (see Jones, 1997; in: Panneels et al., 2024, p 24), so understanding and knowing about the local creative ecosystem is valuable.

4.7 Communication channels

Refining the questions related to communication channels used by their members, Creative Edinburgh can create a more inclusive and flexible experience. A more inclusive approach would be to list the most popular social media platforms used by creatives in their community at the time. If time and resources permit, conducting a quick survey within the membership base to identify these key platforms would be helpful at this stage. Embracing the “other” by including a dedicated text field allows members to add links to their profiles on platforms not explicitly listed, such as [Behance](#) (for graphic design), [Dribbble](#) (for UI/UX design), [VSCO](#) (for photography), [Vimeo](#) (for video creators), or [GitHub](#) (for developers).

By catering to a wider range of platforms in this way, Creative Edinburgh could ensure their membership form reflects the diverse ways creatives showcase their work online. This adopts inclusivity and allows members to connect with others using their preferred platforms. Further, providing more options empowers members to share their most relevant online spaces. This facilitates deeper and more meaningful connections within the community based on shared interests and preferred platforms. It can be a valuable resource for understanding trends in social media usage within the creative community, and how these trends might correlate with demographics. Over time, for example, the data can reveal platform popularity among different creative disciplines and help spot the rise of new platforms and how quickly they are adopted by the creative community. When analysed alongside member demographics, some potential correlations might emerge such as certain creatives favouring newer platforms like TikTok while established platforms might rely on Facebook pages.

4.8 Industry alignment

Creative Edinburgh currently uses its own system to categorise creative sectors within its organisation embroidered and aligned to the 16 Scottish Creative and Cultural Industries. While this system might be comprehensive, there is a window to improve clarity and impact by aligning with internationally recognised standards. Standardisation within the creative industries creates a universal vocabulary, promoting better understanding and stronger partnerships.

4.8.1 Background

In the late 1990s, the UK's Department for Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS, 2001) proposed to group diverse sectors like performing arts, film, advertising, and even software under a single umbrella: the "creative industries". The DCMS defined these industries as those driven by individual creativity, skill, and talent. These industries, they argued, held the potential to generate wealth and jobs through intellectual property. To support this idea, the DCMS began routinely publishing economic data. This data linked the creative sub-sectors to existing national classification systems for industries -SIC (Standard Industrial Classification) codes and occupations – SOC (Standard Occupational Classification) codes. DCMS created a specific set of industries and occupations deemed "creative" for economic measurement purposes. This implied that all other industries and occupations were not "creative" (Bakhshi, 2015).

Although used globally, there are, however, issues with SIC and SOC codes, which are widely acknowledged and which we have written about elsewhere (Panneels et al., 2021). Bakhshi argues that “the creative industries” initiative is widely considered a success. It significantly raised the profile of the creative industries in the eyes of policymakers as this is evident by how quickly other governments adopted the DCMS metrics.

4.8.2 Benefits

We propose that a breakdown of creative sub-sectors and their associated SIC codes could be a key tool for Creative Edinburgh to gain insights into their membership landscape, develop targeted strategies and, ultimately, better serve and advocate for the

thriving creative community in Scotland by linking its membership to national and international data strategies. Using established statistical classifications like SIC and SOC offers additional benefits for data comparability as these codes are used by national and international organisations allowing for comparisons of creative industries data across different regions and countries. Creative Edinburgh can educate its members about industry standards and empower them to categorise their creative endeavours more accurately.

Standardised data would allow Creative Edinburgh to advocate for the creative industries more effectively. Policymakers rely on this data to understand the needs and contributions of different creative sectors. These codes, although problematic in part, might support a coherent collection of accurate and comparable data on the creative workforce providing valuable data into the size, scope, and economic impact of the creative industries in Scotland. This practice could help Creative Edinburgh identify and connect members with relevant funding opportunities aligned with their specific creative sector and allows for a more all-inclusive mapping of the creative industry landscape facilitating strategic planning and development initiatives within the sector. Moreover, aligning with international standards could enhance Creative Edinburgh's recognition as a key membership body representing the creative industries in the region and allows for better networking opportunities for its members within the international creative community.

By knowing the SIC codes associated with each creative sub-sector, Creative Edinburgh could identify which sectors are most heavily represented. This valuable insight might enable them to tailor resources, events, and advocacy efforts to better serve the specific needs of their dominant creative communities. However, the breakdown of creative sub-sectors (see table 4) could also reveal gaps in their membership. If certain sectors are underrepresented, Creative Edinburgh can then develop targeted outreach programs or communication strategies to attract a more diverse membership, ensuring their community reflects the full spectrum of the creative industries in Scotland.

Furthermore, systematic and long term data collected on its membership in a format that can be compared or aligned to other datasets would augment Creative Edinburgh's

advocacy efforts. By understanding the specific SIC codes of their members, they can gather data relevant to those sectors. This data becomes powerful evidence when building arguments for policies that benefit the creative sector as a whole.

With better data, the true size and economic contribution of the self-employed sector can be accurately measured, for example, or data on gender (dis)parities or sector trends. Standardised data could support more reliable analysis of self-employed income trends over time informing policy decisions related to taxation, social security benefits, and support programs for self-employed workers. Comparisons can also be made between different sectors of the self-employed workforce like freelance writers vs. independent contractors to understand income disparities and needs. This can inform economic development strategies and resource allocation to support this growing segment of the workforce. Pinpointing the income of self-employed individuals is a complex task, leading to limited data coverage (Athrow, 2017).

Table 4: Breakdown of the 16-sub sectors of the Creative Industries and associated SIC Codes

Scottish Creative & Cultural Industries	DCMS Codes	SIC 2007
1. Advertising	Advertising and Marketing	SIC 73.11: Advertising agencies
		SIC 73.12: Media representation
2. Architecture	Architecture	SIC 71.11: Architectural activities
3. Visual art	Museums, Galleries and Libraries	SIC 90.03: Artistic creation (70%)
		SIC 47.78/1: Retail sale in commercial art galleries
4. Crafts and Antiques	Crafts	SIC 31.09: Manufacture of other furniture
		SIC 16.29: Manufacture of other wood products (30%)
		SIC 32.12: Manufacture of jewellery and related products
		SIC 32.13: Manufacture of imitation jewellery and related articles

		SIC 23.41 Manufacture of ceramic household and ornamental articles (35%)
		SIC 23.49 Manufacture of other ceramic products (35%)
		SIC 23.13 Manufacture of hollow glass (15%)
		SIC 23.19 Manufacture of other glass (15%)
		SIC 47.79/1: Retail sale of antiques and antique books
		SIC 95.24: Repair of furniture and home furnishings
5. Fashion and textiles	Design (Product, Graphic, Fashion etc.)	SIC 13: Manufacture of textiles (25%)
		SIC 14: Manufacture of wearing apparel (20%)
		SIC 15: Manufacture of leather and related products (20%)
		SIC 74.1: Specialised design activities (25%)
6. Design	Design (Product, Graphic, Fashion etc.)	SIC 71.12/1: Engineering design activities for industrial process and production
		SIC 74.1: Specialised design activities (75%)
7. Performing arts	Music, Performing & Visual Arts	SIC 90.01: Performing arts
		SIC 90.02: Support activities to performing arts
		SIC 90.04: Operation of arts facilities
		SIC 78.10/1: Motion picture, television and other theatrical casting
8. Music	Music, Performing & Visual Arts	SIC 59.2: Sound recording and music publishing activities
		SIC 18.20/1: Reproduction of sound recording
		SIC 32.2: Manufacture of musical instruments
9. Photography	Film, TV, Video, Radio & Photography	SIC 74.20/1: Portrait photographic activities
		SIC 74.20/2: Other specialist photography (not including portrait photography)
		SIC 74.20/9: Other photographic activities (not including portrait and other specialist photography and film processing) n.e.c.

10. Film and video	Film, TV, Video, Radio & Photography	SIC 18.20/2: Reproduction of video recording
		SIC 59.11/1: Motion picture production activities
		SIC 59.11/2: Video production activities
		SIC 59.12: Motion picture, video and television programme post-production activities (25%)
		SIC 59.13/1: Motion picture distribution activities
		SIC 59.13/2: Video distribution activities
		SIC 59.14: Motion picture projection activities
11. Computer Games		SIC 58.21: Publishing of computer games
		SIC 62.01/1: Ready-made interactive leisure and entertainment software development
12. Radio and TV		SIC 59.11/3: Television programme production activities
		SIC 59.13/3: Television programme distribution activities
	Film, TV, Video, Radio & Photography	SIC 59.12: Motion picture, video and television programme post-production activities (75%)
		SIC 60.1: Radio broadcasting
		SIC 60.2: Television programming and broadcasting activities
13. Writing and Publishing		SIC 90.03: Artistic creation (30%)
		SIC 58.11: Book publishing
		SIC 58.13: Publishing of newspapers

		SIC 58.14: Publishing of journals and periodicals
	Publishing	SIC 58.19: Other publishing activities
		SIC 18.11: Printing of newspapers
		SIC 18.129: Other printing (not labels)
		SIC 18.13: Pre press and media services
		SIC 63.91: News agency activities
14. Libraries and archives		SIC 91.01: Libraries and archive activities
15. Software/electronic publishing		SIC 58.29 Other software publishing
	Tech - IT, Software, Hardware and Computer Services	SIC 62.01/2: Business and domestic software development
		SIC 62.02: Computer consultancy activities
16. Cultural education		SIC 85.52: Cultural Education

4.8.3 Learning from South of Scotland Enterprise (SOSE)

SOSE, a new development agency for businesses and enterprising communities throughout Dumfries and Galloway and the Scottish Borders, undertook a regional mapping exercise to understand the size and scope of the regional creative industries sector, as part of their economic remit. SOSE developed a comprehensive table that breaks down various creative sub-sectors like film and video into very specific fields like cinematographer, editor. This initiative highlights the importance of understanding member specialties within the creative sector as it allows for a detailed breakdown to identify creatives with a high degree of precision, understanding not just their broad creative area but their specific role within that sector. By sharing the table below with Creative Edinburgh, SOSE and in particular Strategy Manager - Cultural and Creative Capital Strategy, Mark Geddes, provided a valuable example of how to gather more granular data on their creative community.

Table 5: Creative industries sub-sector breakdown (reproduced with permission from Mark Geddes, SOSE)

Advertising	Computer Games	Crafts	Film and Video
Account management	Animator	Basketry, willow weaving	Actor
Art director	Application developer	Bookbinding	Aerial photography
Brand designer	Cinematographer	Ceramics	Animator
Copywriter	Computer Programmer	Furniture Making	Art director
Creative director	Distributor	Glass Working	Casting director
Data analyst	Esports promoter	Jewellery	Choreographer
Digital designer	Game designer	Leather Working	Cinema exhibition
Graphic Designer	Game tester	Metal Working	Cinematographer
Illustrator	Games writer	Millinery	Costume designer
Marketing manager	Graphic designer	Mosaics	Director
Media management	Level designer	Paper Making	Distributor
Photographer	Marketing manager	Silver/Goldsmithing	Editor
Print designer	Media lawyer	Stone Working	Electrician, spark
Public relations	Music composer	Textiles - weaving, felting	Fight director
SEO specialist	Producer	Wood Working	Film lawyer
Social Media copywriter	Production manager		Filmmaker
Software developer	Public relations	Design	Foley artist
	Quality assurance	Graphic designer	Greensman
	Software developer	Interior designer	Grip, camera
Architecture	Sound engineer	Photographer	Hair and makeup artist
Architect	Special effects	Art director	Lighting, gaffer
Architectural Technician		Animation designer	Line producer, accounts
Building surveyor	Cultural Education	Product designer	Location management
Draughtsman	Educator	Digital designer	Management agent
Historic inspector	Lecturer	Brand designer	Marketing manager
Interior designer	Teacher	Print designer	Media management
Project manager		Packaging design	Music composer
Structural engineer			Photographer

Town planner			Producer
			Production management
			Prop creator
			Public relations
			Sales agent
			Script writer
			Set designer
			Sound engineer
			Special effects

Fashion and Textiles	Music	Performing Arts	Radio and TV
Copywriter	Agent	Actor	Actor
Costume designer	Choreographer	Art director	Art director
Dyers	Disc Jockey	Choreographer	Broadcaster
Embroidery machinist	Event management	Costume designer	Casting director
Fashion designer	Hair and makeup artist	Dancer	Choreographer
Fashion illustrator	Instrument technician	Director	Cinematographer
Fashion merchandiser	Lighting engineer	Drama therapist	Costume designer
Finishers	Management agent	Fight director	Director
Garment technologist	Manufacturer	Hair and makeup artist	Disc Jockey
Graphic designer	Marketing manager	Lighting engineer	Distributor
Linker, sewer	Music composer	Management agent	Editor
Machine programmers	Music director	Marketing manager	Electrician, spark
Makeup artist	Music editor	Playwright	Fight director
Mender, danner	Music journalist	Producer	Filmmaker
Pattern grader	Music lawyer	Screenwriter	Foley artist
Photographer	Music promotion	Set designer	Greensman
Production management	Music teacher	Sound designer	Grip, camera
Sewing machinists	Music video director	Sound technician	Hair and makeup artist
Textile designer	Musician	Stage manager	Lighting, gaffer
Visual merchandiser	Photographer	Teacher	Line producer, accounts

Weaver	Production manager	Theatre director	Location management
	Public relations	Theatre performer	Management agent
Heritage	Publisher	Theatre technician	Marketing manager
Archaeologist	Record Producer		Media lawyer
Archivist	Singer	Photography	Media management
Conservator	Songwriter	Aerial Photography	Music composer
Customer services	Sound engineer	Photographer	Photographer
Exhibition's officer	Sound production		Producer
Genealogist	Stage manager		Production management
Heritage manager	Sales agent		Prop creator
Heritage officer			Public relations
Museum curator			Script writer
Museum educator			Set designer
Museum management			Sound engineer
			Special effects
Software / Electronic Publishing		Visual Arts	Writing and Publishing
Application developer		Artist	Author
Back-end developer		Ceramics	Book publisher
Business analyst		Drawing	Contract manager
Cloud engineer		Filmmaking	Copy editor
Computer programmer		Illustrator	Copywriter
Copywriter		Painter	Distributor
Data analyst		Performing artist	Graphic designer
Embedded system engineer		Photography	Illustrator
Front-end developer		Printmaker	Literary lawyer
Full-stack developer		Sculptor	Management agent
Game developer			Marketing management
Graphic designer			Media management
Language developer			Printer
Mobile test engineer			Production manager
Photographer			Proof-reader
Public relations			Public relations

Publisher		Publicist
Quality assurance		Rights manager
SEO specialist		Sales agent
Social Media copywriter		
Software developer		
User experience designer		

By learning from SOSE's best practices, Creative Edinburgh can refine its approach, strengthen its impact, and become an even more valuable resource for Scotland's thriving creative sector. More concretely, by following and implementing this idea, Creative Edinburgh can achieve several benefits such as stronger member engagement by tailored communication and resources that resonates better with members, enhanced advocacy efforts as the data gathered from specific creative fields strengthens Creative Edinburgh's advocacy efforts further allowing them to champion the needs of their diverse membership more effectively. Moreover, this level of member understanding sets Creative Edinburgh apart as it might give them a competitive advantage. They can position themselves as a leading organisation that truly understands and supports the multifaceted creative community in Scotland. On the practical side, adding too many options during sign-up can overwhelm members and decrease completion rates. Creative Edinburgh might consider a two-step approach - a broad sector selection followed by an optional field for further specialisation.

4.9 Emergent fields

The previous section outlined the advantages of aligning with standardised codes, such as improved communication, policy advocacy, and access to targeted resources. These benefits are undeniable and can empower Creative Edinburgh to represent its members more effectively.

However, the creative landscape is constantly evolving, with new fields and practices emerging all the time. Standardised codes might not always perfectly capture these "emergent fields". Creative Edinburgh can provide a platform for members to express and represent these emerging fields, even if they are not explicitly covered by standardised

codes. This empowers new voices to be heard within the community and encourages innovation. Actively involving members in identifying and capturing emergent fields, Creative Edinburgh leverages its grassroots nature. This member participation helps the organisation stay relevant and adapt to the ever-changing creative landscape. This could potentially feed into a contribution towards refinement of the creative sector codes backed by data in the future, even if these codes are agreed on and decided internationally.

Creative Edinburgh can achieve a balance between standardisation and recognising emergent fields in practice by allowing members to identify with an "Other" category and elaborate on their specific field within the creative industries. This captures both standardised and emerging fields. After this, the organisation could periodically review the codes and consider member input regarding potential updates to reflect the evolving creative landscape.

4.10 Refining employment details

The current approach to collecting employment details on the Creative Edinburgh membership form can be improved for clarity and to gather more nuanced data. By implementing the following refinements, categorised for clarity, privacy, and data depth, Creative Edinburgh can achieve a more user-friendly and informative membership form.

- **Simplifying and respecting privacy:** Instead of "What status do you primarily identify with currently," using a simpler and more direct question like "What is your current employment status?" This reduces ambiguity and is easier for members to understand. Having a "prefer not to say" option for members who wish to keep their employment status private is beneficial as these respects their privacy while still allowing others to share their information.
- **Self-employment:** The UK government recognises both freelancers and sole traders as self-employed (UK Government, n.d.). The form can offer separate options for "Freelancer" and "Sole Trader" to capture this distinction. This provides valuable insights into the specific makeup of the creative community. While a direct question about tax filing might be too personal, consider adding an optional question like, "Do you file your own self-employment taxes?" This can provide

some indication of whether a member operates as a sole trader or under a different structure.

- **Understanding businesses:** The current form includes a company field within the employment status section. If a member identifies as a company, a separate question can be added later in the form specifically asking, "Are you the owner/founder of this company?" Further, if a member identifies as a business owner, adding a question about "How long have you been in the creative business?" with options like, "Less than 1 year," "1-2 years," "3-5 years" etc. can be helpful. This provides insights into the experience level and longevity of creative businesses within the membership.

4.11 Tools for advancing data analysis

Considering goals of scaling member data, advanced analysis, and budget-friendliness, we have looked at appropriate technologies for data analysis and provide several appropriate software options to explore:

4.11.1 Open-source solutions

We suggest solutions that are cost-effective but require data science knowledge. [R](#) & [Python](#) for example are powerful programming languages with extensive data science libraries like pandas, scikit-learn, and TensorFlow. They offer complete control and flexibility but require coding expertise. Up-front learning is needed, but a wealth of free online resources exists. They are free and open-source and are highly customisable and powerful. Additionally, there is a large developer community and learning resources.

4.11.2 Cloud-based business intelligence tools

The cloud based business intelligence solutions we have identified as appropriate to this context are scalable, user-friendly and come with varying cost. One of them being [Microsoft power BI](#) which is a well-known Business Intelligence tool with a user-friendly interface and excellent visualisation capabilities. It integrates well with other Microsoft products and offers various pricing tiers. Another popular choice is [Tableau](#) known for its drag-and-drop functionality and interactive dashboards. It has a free version with limitations, and paid plans offer more features. Lastly there is [Google's Looker studio](#), a

free BI tool that allows data exploration and visualisation. It integrates seamlessly with Google Sheets and other Google products.

All three are scalable to accommodate a growing member base. Having a user-friendly interface with drag-and-drop functionality is easier to learn especially when they have a pre-built dashboards and visualisations. Although, they can be expensive for advanced features and large datasets and may require some technical knowledge for data manipulation.

4.11.3 Hybrid approach

The best practical approach in the current scenario is to combine cost-effectiveness and user-friendliness of Excel or Google sheets by continuing their use for basic data entry and initial analysis. Its strength lies in collaboration and ease of access. On the other hand, an open-source tool for advanced analysis can be used as needs evolve, by incorporating Python, R or Power BI for specific data analysis and visualisation tasks. These skills can be learned progressively or specific tasks can be considered for outsourcing

This approach leverages existing familiarity with Google Sheets or Excel and allows gradual introduction of data science tools by data migration as most BI tools offer data import options from spreadsheets like Excel which ensures a smooth transition.

5 AI and ML applications

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have the potential to revolutionise the creative sector, and Creative Edinburgh can be at the forefront of this transformation. AI excels at tasks requiring pattern recognition and data analysis and can help facilitate and advance insights into data for Creative Edinburgh and the creative industries at large. Implementing or using AI/ML usually takes some expert knowledge both of the technologies themselves and the appropriateness of their use and potential risks (e.g. biases that may have particular ED&I or privacy aspects). Following are long-term recommendations for organisations that might be employed in the future:

- *Personalised member support:* Based on a member's profile (skills, interests), the system could suggest relevant workshops like "Social Media Marketing for Musicians" for a musician member.
- *Targeted communication and resources:* Instead of generic emails, AI can be used to personalise newsletters and updates based on member data. For instance, [Mailchimp](#) already used by Creative Edinburgh utilises AI to suggest catchy and relevant subject lines that might improve email open rates.
- *Improved member insights:* Analyse surveys, feedback forms, and social media data to understand member needs and preferences. This allows for continuous improvement of services and programs. For example, utilise social media listening tools to gather relevant data from platforms like Instagram, Twitter and Facebook. Tools like [Brandwatch](#) can help and focus on keywords and mentions related to Creative Edinburgh, member experiences, and specific services offered.

Regarding the specific deployment of AI and ML in the Creative Industries, there are multiple possibilities, connected of course with the need for discussions around data

privacy, copyright issues, etc. The CI project on [Creativity and AI](#) created a report⁹ on the outcomes of this demonstrator project, which focused on working with creatives in Scotland to understand their opinions of, needs for and ideas around AI. Below are some suggestions as to how AI and ML could be used in the creative sector, and including organisations such as CE:

- Content personalization and targeting: AI can personalize content recommendations for audiences on streaming platforms or social media.
- Enhanced collaboration and workflows: Streamline project workflows by automating scheduling, resource allocation, and progress tracking. Organize and categorize creative assets, making them easier to find and reuse, improving collaboration within creative teams.
- Content creation and design: AI-powered tools can assist with tasks like: generating logo variations, color palettes, or mood boards for designers. Composing musical samples, melodies, or background sounds for musicians. Or even suggesting story outlines or overcoming writer's block for writers.

The need for ED&I discussions around the datafication and AI and ML aspects regarding the creative industries must be emphasized. While creatives do not generally refuse the idea of AI (Black et al, 2024), there are numerous concerns, fears and needs that must be addressed, specifically when it comes to the creative industries sector. Organisations like Creative Edinburgh can help by providing workshops, legal and copyright related advise and their role can become even more important and nuanced in the future as a relevant liaison and living repository for creatives and their needs related to creativity and AI.

⁹ Black, Suzanne R., Bilbao, Stefan, Moruzzi, Caterina, Osborne, Nicola, Terras, Melissa, and Zeller, Frauke. (2024). The Future of Creativity and AI: Views from the Scottish Creative Industries. A Report from Creative Informatics. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10805253>

6 Membership Survey Recommendations

Based on the above discussions, we introduce a breakdown of the suggested amendments for the Creative Edinburgh membership survey, including those fields that currently exist and that we suggest keeping. Note that we also applied the ‘quality over quantity mandate (or ‘be economical mandate’), which means that while it would certainly be interesting to add more questions to the survey, we acknowledge survey method guidelines that state too many questions lead to lower completion rates. Thus, we re-evaluated every existing question, and questions we deemed interesting to be added in several iterations against the mandate of being economical and mindful of people’s time and patience. Table 6 below shows the outcome of this process, with new questions being highlighted.

The revised survey is not just about collecting data. It is about equipping Creative Edinburgh to become a data-driven champion for the creative sector by advocating for its members and shaping a brighter future for the creative industries in Scotland. A more concise form leads to higher completion rates, potentially improving membership acquisition. The recognition of emerging fields within the standardised code framework, for example, ensures the system adapts to industry evolution, too. The drive to amend the current survey reflects professionalism and user-centricity, aligning with Creative Edinburgh’s commitment to its members. It is also one of the ways to strike a balance between collecting necessary data and respecting user privacy helping Creative Edinburgh to build a better and more meaningful understanding of its members. The benefits extend far beyond the membership itself. The key argument is that this will unlock the true potential of data for Creative Edinburgh and the wider creative sector by using accurate and comprehensive data collected through the application, and Creative Edinburgh can advocate for the creative sector with a powerful voice. They can present policymakers and industry partners with compelling data-driven arguments that highlight the needs and contributions of creatives in Scotland.

Secondly, the standardised data framework allows Creative Edinburgh to share valuable insights with sectoral bodies. This utilisation of the aggregated and of the anonymised data can inform policy development, resource allocation, and overall support for the creative sector at large. And finally, with a strong foundation of data, Creative Edinburgh can identify trends and needs within the creative community allowing them to forge strategic partnerships with industry leaders, collaboration and driving innovation within the sector.

Table 6: Amended Membership Survey Overview (amendments highlighted in green)

Personal details	Note	Criteria
First name & last name	Default field by Join It	Required
Email	Default field by Join It	Required
Gender	With a spectrum of options beyond male or female with a "prefer not to say"	Required
Postcode	Emphasise data privacy and anonymisation for postcode usage.	Required
Communication channels		
Phone		Optional
Profile photo		Optional
Website		Optional
Social media integration	Offer a streamlined selection of the most popular platforms e.g. Instagram, Facebook, X, LinkedIn with an "other" option and text field for less common platforms.	Optional
Understanding the members		
Why did you join Creative Edinburgh?	Multiple choice or open-ended format	Required
Which sector of the Creative Industries do you primarily work in?	Align with international codes (SIC/SOC) and offer an "other" category with a text field for capturing emerging fields.	Required
Tell us about yourself and your creative work?	Provide a text field for members to elaborate on themselves and their creative work.	Required
Employment details		

What is your current employment status?	Simplified options like employed, self-employed (freelancer/sole trader), student, unemployed, retired, prefer not to say.	Required
What is your income range in the creative field?	Provide commonly used income ranges to choose from.	Optional
Do you own a company?	If member selects "company" in employment status.	Optional
Do you currently file your own self-employment tax returns?	Optional for deeper insights	Optional

The additional optional questions related to sexuality, nationality or disability, which so far have been asked in the first email upon signing up (see above, section 3), can also be added to the survey as an optional question in order to avoid having to send follow-up emails. A question related to whether or not members have care giving responsibilities, which represents a potentially large group within the creative sector, can also be added. Creative Edinburgh has been organising a range of events in the past for caretakers and thus contributed to the often still scarce resources of additional support for this group.

7 User Centricity

We suggest keeping the user (i.e. the data provider) at the centre of the data collection process is paramount to building a sustainable and trusted data gathering infrastructure. This means that clear and transparent communication should always be integral to each question set asked in the survey. The language used should also be understandable to a broad audience, avoiding too many technical terms. User feedback and interaction also must be included, making it possible for everyone to ask questions and provide feedback. Overall, designing a survey must comply with a range of guidelines and principles: Apart from quantitative and qualitative research paradigms, inductive and deductive research approaches, a survey must be based on ED&I principles as well as follow standardised legal and privacy norms. To be fully user centric, however, one can use knowledge and experience from a range of related fields, such as User Experience (UX) research methods (see, for example, Benyon, 2019) and Interaction Design Principles (see, for example, Preece, Rogers, & Sharp, 2023). While the first focuses on creating successful user experiences for applications including interactive websites, surveys can also be included here. The latter, Interaction Design Principles, traditionally focus on applications in the area of Human-Computer Interaction Design, but its mandate of iterative design (see above, section 1.1) should also be applied in the successful design of a membership survey.

Finally, in our project we also included Creative Edinburgh as an important user – albeit being here the administrating unit of the survey. Nevertheless, when administrating a survey, each creator should always ask: “What answer do I want and need from this question?” While it is interesting to ask many questions, not all are ultimately relevant for the person or organisation who is asking them. This goes hand in hand with the ‘quality-over-quantity’ mandate, that is to keep any questionnaire as brief as possible for the sake of each participants’ time.

8 Data Circularity

In the context of Creative Edinburgh and its members, we want to introduce the concept of “data circularity” to refer to a two-way flow of information between the organisation and its creative community. A traditional data flow typically is when organisations collect data from their members using surveys, sign-up applications but the data flow is one-directional. On the other hand, data circularity is an approach that emphasises a more reciprocal exchange where members are also encouraged to contribute data and receive value in return as it has the potential to empower creatives to achieve a sense of community and shared purpose¹⁰.

This reciprocal flow of data offers several benefits. When members feel their data is being used to benefit them such as informing relevant resources or advocacy efforts, they are more likely to be engaged and contribute accurate information. Members feel like they have a voice in shaping the organisation's direction through their data contributions.

By implementing data circularity effectively, Creative Edinburgh can build stronger relationships with its members, gain deeper insights into the creative community, and ultimately better serve the needs of Scotland's creative sector. At this stage, robust data security practices and clear communication about data usage are crucial to maintain member trust and finding the right balance between collecting valuable data and overwhelming members is important. Examples of implementing data circularity for Creative Edinburgh and other related organisations can be:

- *Interactive member surveys*: Going beyond basic demographics and asking for feedback on current services and suggestions for improvement. Communicating how the data informed the development of programming and services.

¹⁰ This concept was coined by Inge Panneels during the Creative Informatics ‘Policy Hack Day: Data, Data. Everywhere (Creative Horizon 5)’ workshops on data organised in September 2022.

- *Project reporting platform:* Developing a system for members to easily submit data about their creative projects like [members directory](#) initiative by Creative Edinburgh. This contributes to industry data and could connect them with potential collaborators. Meanwhile, members having the ability to choose what information is shared publicly and what remains private, safeguards sensitive details while promoting professional networking.
- *Data-driven communication:* Using member data to tailor newsletters, regional updates and dedicated annual reports for specific creative sectors in the region. This ensures information is relevant and valuable to specific creative sectors. By seeing how their individual journeys align with broader patterns, members can gain a deeper understanding of their place within the creative landscape and would be willing to share meaningful data. Additionally, by contributing data about emergent and new fields, members actively participate in the evolution of Creative Edinburgh.
- *Tailored local offerings:* Based on geographic data, Creative Edinburgh can offer personalised experiences with localised events, resources, and opportunities relevant to a member's region. Members may gain access to valuable data and trends specific to their creative sector in their region, providing valuable insights for career development.

9 EDI Considerations

Data collection is a crucial aspect in creative industries, but it must be done responsibly and ethically. At the same time, it is also vital to make sure that existing data gaps are being closed in order to be as inclusive as possible in any data mapping activity. Previous research found, for example, that freelancers and charities are often not included in existing data maps of the creative industries sector. This stands against the fact that freelancers make up one of the biggest groups in the creative industries sectors as with 32% self-employed, the creative sector has a much higher rate of freelancers compared to the overall UK workforce (16%) (DCMS, 2021). Closing this gap can then also have a positive circularity aspect by feeding back to policy makers and funders, giving them a more accurate landscape of the sector and inspiring new ways of support.

Considering transparency and user trust, explaining what data is being collected, how it will be used, and with whom it might be shared is an efficient and ethical data practice. Data collected for regional analysis should be anonymised to protect member privacy and linked to a comprehensive privacy policy that outlines data collection practices in detail

On the other hand, implementing for data security and compliance, strong data security measures to protect member information from unauthorised access is vital. For this, a clear data retention policy should be developed which outlines how long data is stored and the process for member deletion requests. Also, ensuring data collection practices comply with relevant data privacy regulations such as the Data Protection Act 2018 (based upon GDPR principles).

As data can be used to advocate for policy changes that benefit the creative sector in Scotland and beyond, by prioritising transparency, user trust, and responsible data practices, Creative Edinburgh and other such organisations can ensure its revamped application gathers valuable information while respecting member privacy. This exercise will bring about a positive and ethical approach to data collection, ultimately strengthening the organisation's relationship with its creative community.

10 Conclusion and Recommendations

From our work with Creative Edinburgh and examining their data infrastructure and collection methods, we recommend three main principles that we argue should support the development of better data collection infrastructures of membership organisations and other grassroots organisations in the creative industries. These are:

- 1. *User-Centricity*:** Data alone cannot speak for a community. When it comes to using data as a tool to gauge a better understanding of who does what, when and how in a community, then a user-centric approach is pivotal. This means, when designing a data collection framework, it is critical to already have a sound understanding of the community, its needs, and in how far and what data could help to better depict the community. Thus, working with the main stakeholders (i.e. its members or core constituents) provides the necessary core understanding. This puts the user at the centre, rather than the data.
- 2. *ED&I*:** This key-term (Equality, Diversity and Inclusion) relates to the first principle insofar as it is necessary to understand and respect a community's and its individual members' privacy rights/concerns, and their needs. It is also important to empower the creative community by not just collecting their data but to also demonstrate the value of their data to the collective benefit, show them how they can collect data themselves, to what ends, and what to do with it. It is also clear that a large set of quantitative data alone does not provide insights but that some data skills are required to be able to interpret and understand the data. ED&I also means that a data collection approach should reflect the inherent diversity of the community, meaning it needs to provide the opportunity to also input 'outlier' data, such as detailed aspects of one's business, personal economic and social circumstances, etc. Acknowledging that traditional statistical data approaches tend to overlook minorities, and intersectional considerations, is the first step. Working together with the community's stakeholders to then integrate these aspects is the necessary second step.

3. **Data-Circularity:** We introduce this term here to connect to the ‘bigger picture’, that is ensures that the collected data can also be used to map onto other, formal and informal data initiatives and that data collection does not just benefit those collecting it (usually organisational or institutional entities), but also benefits the sector itself, and particularly those creative businesses whose data is being collected. A standardised data framework would allow valuable insights to be shared with sectoral bodies. This use of the aggregated and of the anonymised data can inform policy development, resource allocation, and overall support for the creative sector at large, including those at grassroots level. In short, data should be of value and use to all, not just policymakers.

From the three main principles, we provide the following key recommendations, which can also be used by other organisations looking into data as a powerful tool to support their communities.

User-Centricity Recommendations:

13. Work with relevant stakeholders of the community to gain first-hand understanding of the kind of data that is needed – develop the main questions that the community aims to answer through their data collection initiative
14. Adapt the overall data collection plan to the actual economic setting of those that will be responsible for the data collection and analysis – check their personnel availability, expertise, etc
15. Always follow the mandate ‘quality over quantity’ – triple-check each question on the survey whether it is really necessary or not.

ED&I Recommendations:

16. Make sure the overall survey follows ED&I considerations, be mindful of how minorities who historically have been overlooked might perceive questions that reflect a standardised Western world view.
17. Make sure to show how members can entirely delete or change the information they provided. Be very transparent and clear which information that is provided will

be displayed publicly, anonymized or not, and which stays private/within the data collecting organization.

18. Be very sure about the purpose and reason for asking questions/collecting data. This communicates a peer-level, where those that provide information feel like they are in control of the whole data collection process (also part of the data circularity principle).

Data-Circularity Recommendations:

19. Work with stakeholders that could function as broadcasters in the community and can help to increase support and data provision
20. Check what formal data collection/surveying structures are already in place from government organizations and find out how data-circularity could work in both ways. Make sure to use similar or matching variables/categories
21. Look out for other examples of existing data collection approaches – learn from best practice.
22. Make sure data collection follows a logical flow that mirrors how people typically provide information.
23. Consider relevant cross-tabulation approaches for the analysis, check which variables would be useful to pair with other variables.
24. Offer different levels of personal information questions, reflecting different membership tiers that demand different levels of commitment. Members should feel in that they get something back for providing more information.

We acknowledge that a more holistic data infrastructure for and by the creative industries requires a joint up approach between those who operate at the grassroots organisations (micro), such as Creative Edinburgh and others, such as SOSE, who operate at regional policy level (meso), and national government agencies (macro), such as DCMS or Scottish Government. Each has their own specific data infrastructure collection requirements and different governance by which it has to operate. But we contend that by understanding the functionality of the data collection methods and infrastructure better, and understanding better why, and which data is collected benefits the creative industries at large. We suggest that there is enormous potential in unlocking these data

infrastructures at these three levels and align them better to each other to support better insights and data circularity.

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13 Appendix

13.1 Other membership management platforms

Choosing the best membership management platform (MMP) is crucial for any organisation and choosing the right platform depends on specific needs and factors like budget, membership size, desired features, and technical expertise.

Below is a breakdown of how contemporary platforms like Mighty Networks, Hivebrite, Join It, Google Forms, and Wild Apricot compare in terms of their main features, pricing, ease of use, scalability, and integration features:

Feature Focus

<u>Mighty Networks:</u>	Focuses on building online communities with features like discussion forums, groups, and courses. Ideal for fostering member engagement and interaction.
<u>Hivebrite:</u>	Caters to membership organisations, particularly those with alumni networks. Offers strong CRM (Customer Relationship Management) capabilities and event management tools.
<u>Join It:</u>	Streamlines repetitive membership management tasks with automation features. Ideal for organisations with straightforward membership needs and a focus on online payments.
<u>Google Forms:</u>	A free, basic option for collecting membership applications and basic information. Lacks advanced features for managing ongoing memberships.
<u>Wild Apricot:</u>	A comprehensive MMP with features for membership management, communication tools, event management, and financial tracking. Well-suited for organisations of all sizes with diverse membership needs.

Pricing

Mighty Networks	Pricing varies based on features and number of members. Can be cost-prohibitive for smaller organisations.
Hivebrite	Custom quotes based on needs. Generally, more expensive than Join It and Wild Apricot.
Join It	Affordable, tiered pricing plans based on number of members. Offers a free trial without needing a credit card information.
Google Forms	Free.
Wild Apricot	Tiered pricing based on features and number of members. Offers a free trial.

Ease of Use

Mighty Networks	User-friendly interface with a focus on building engaging online communities. Learning curve for advanced features.
Hivebrite	More complex interface catering to experienced users. Steeper learning curve.
Join It	Simple and intuitive interface. Ideal for organisations with limited technical expertise.
Google Forms	Very easy to use for basic data collection, but lacks comprehensive membership management features.
Wild Apricot	User-friendly with a range of features. May require some training for advanced functionalities.

Scalability

Mighty Networks	Scalable to accommodate growing memberships, but pricing reflects member size.
Hivebrite	Highly scalable for large organisations with complex membership structures.
Join It	Scales well for smaller to mid-sized organisations. May not be ideal for very large memberships.

Google Forms	Not suitable for ongoing membership management.
Wild Apricot	Highly scalable with plans to accommodate various membership sizes.

Integration Features

Mighty Networks	Offers integrations with popular tools like email marketing platforms and payment processors.
Hivebrite	Integrates with various CRM and event management platforms.
Join It	Offers limited integration options.
Google Forms	Integrates with Google Sheets and other Google products.
Wild Apricot	Offers a wider range of integrations with popular business tools.

13.2 Appendix B: Step by step guide for data cleaning and analysis

The step-by-step guide is designed for analysing trends and facilitates this process even for those without expertise in handling data. The raw data originates from the “Join It” membership platform, which Creative Edinburgh utilises for managing memberships. It serves as an illustration of how to handle data cleaning and analysis.

Data cleaning

Ensuring consistent data formats and addressing missing values or outliers allows you to create reliable connections between different data points.

Step 1. Export membership platform data

Export the data in csv or .xls file format. Ensure that the data is in a tabular format of rows and columns with similar data in each column, all columns and rows visible. In the case of Creative Edinburgh, they use ‘Join It’ membership platform which allows for customised data exports. Select specific columns relevant to your analysis, enabling you to focus on

trends. This initial data, unmanipulated for further analysis, will be referred to as "Raw" sheet in this guide. The green columns in the example (for illustrative purposes all fields are filled with placeholder data) represent categories not currently included in the membership survey.

Tip: Create a backup copy of the original data in a separate workbook.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
1	email	first_name	last_name	membership_membership_type_id		external_id	status	joined_date	expiration_date	rebilling_date	renewals	birthday	company	zuguwsbsjw	job_title	phone	gender
2	Email Address as First name Last name Name of Member Unique ID of a Member ID assigned Status of a Member Joined Date Expiration Date Rebilling Date as List of Renewal Birthday associated Company associated Income bracket Job Title associated Phone associated Gender																
3	abc@gmail.com	F1	L1	Core	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2024-02-01	2028-02-08					5k-10k			female
4	def@gmail.com	F2	L2	Plus	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2020-02-15	2028-02-08					10k-20k			male
5	1@gmail.com	F3	L3	Student	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2021-02-15	2028-02-08					20k-30k			do not
6	2@gmail.com	F4	L4	Premium	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12	2028-02-08					less than 5k			male
7	123@gmail.com	F5	L5	Core	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2023-02-08	2028-02-08					30k-40k			female
8	345@gmail.com	F6	L6	Student	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12	2028-02-08					40k-50k			female
9	678@gmail.com	F7	L7	Business	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2019-02-12	2028-02-08					more than 50k			female
10	6700@gmail.com	F8	L8	Core	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2021-02-15	2028-02-08					10k-20k			male
11	45@gmail.com	F9	L9	Core	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2023-02-08	2028-02-08					20k-30k			female
12	abc@gmail.com	F1	L1	Core	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2024-02-01	2028-02-08					5k-10k			female
13	def@gmail.com	F2	L2	Plus	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2020-02-15	2028-02-08					10k-20k			male
14	1@gmail.com	F3	L3	Student	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2021-02-15	2028-02-08					20k-30k			do not
15	2@gmail.com	F4	L4	Premium	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12	2028-02-08					less than 5k			female
16	123@gmail.com	F5	L5	Core	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2023-02-08	2028-02-08					30k-40k			female
17	345@gmail.com	F6	L6	Student	m95XdIdZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12	2028-02-08					40k-50k			female

Figure 1: An example screenshot in a spreadsheet format.

Step 2. Create a data cleaning sheet

Next step is to create a new sheet for data cleaning. In your spreadsheet application, go to the sheet menu and choose "Insert sheet" or a similar option. Rename the new sheet as "Data Cleaning" as shown in Figure 2. The "Data Cleaning" sheet is where you will perform tasks to improve data quality for analysis. This may involve correcting formatting inconsistencies, handling missing values, or standardising data entries.

Figure 2: A new sheet called as "data cleaning."

Step 3. Select columns for analysis

Identify the columns containing data crucial for your analysis in the "Raw" sheet. Select those column headers and copy them. In the "Data Cleaning" sheet, paste them into the desired starting cell (usually cell A1). The reason behind this is that omitting irrelevant columns helps streamline the data cleaning process and also reduces file size.

To colour the header row - click on any cell within the header row (the top row containing column labels). This will select the entire row. Within the formatting options on the toolbar, find the section for "fill" or "background." This will allow you to choose a colour for the selected cells. Click on your desired colour to apply it to the header row just as show in Figure 3.

Tip: Many spreadsheet programs offer additional formatting options beyond fill colour. You can experiment with font styles, bolding, text alignment, and borders to enhance the visual distinction of your headers.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector	Gender (not currently in use)	Income bracket(not currently in use)	Postcode	Joined Date	Expiration Date
4										
5										
7										
8										
9										
13										
14										
16										
17										
18										
22										
23										
25										
26										

Figure 2: Select columns for analysis.

Step 4. Copy data from raw sheet to data cleaning

Step 4.1

In the "Data Cleaning" sheet, click on the cell where you want the copied data to appear.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1							Income bracket(not currently in use)			
4	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector	Gender (not currently in use)		Postcode	Joined Date	Expiration Date
5										
7										
8										
9										
13										

Figure 4: For instance, A4 cell is highlighted here.

Step 4.2

Type an equal sign (=) in the selected cell.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1							Income bracket(not currently in use)			
4	=									
5					mf95XdLjGZ2LW2ikw					
7										
8										
9										
13										
14										

Figure 5: Enter formula.

Step 4.3

Click on the corresponding cell in the "Raw" sheet that contains the first data point you want to copy. This creates a cell reference in the formula, in this case it is 'Raw! E3' as this example, we want to copy the membership ID.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1		name	last_name	membership	membership_type_id	external_id	status	joined_date
2	'Data Cleaning'!A4	First name	Last name	Name of Mem	Unique ID of a Members	ID assigned	Status of a Mem	Joined Date
3	=Raw!E3	F1	L1	Core	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2024-02-01
4	def@gmail.com	F2	L2	Plus	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2020-02-15
5	1@gmail.com	F3	L3	Student	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2021-02-15
6	2@gmail.com	F4	L4	Premium	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12
7	123@gmail.com	F5	L5	Core	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2023-02-08
8	345@gmail.com	F6	L6	Student	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12
9	678@gmail.com	F7	L7	Business	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2019-02-12
10	6700@gmail.com	F8	L8	Core	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2021-02-15
11	45@gmail.com	F9	L9	Core	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2023-02-08
12	abc@gmail.com	F1	L1	Core	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2024-02-01
13	def@gmail.com	F2	L2	Plus	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2020-02-15
14	1@gmail.com	F3	L3	Student	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2021-02-15
15	2@gmail.com	F4	L4	Premium	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12
16	123@gmail.com	F5	L5	Core	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Expired	2023-02-08
17	345@gmail.com	F6	L6	Student	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Active	2019-02-12

Figure 6: Reference the raw data cell

Step 4.4

Hit the Enter key on your keyboard. The value from the referenced cell in the "Raw" sheet will appear in the "Data Cleaning" sheet as shown in Figure 7.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1							Income bracket(not currently in use)	
	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector	Gender (not currently in use)		Postcode
4	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw							
5								
7								
8								
9								
13								
14								
16								
17								
18								
22								
23								
25								
26								
27								
31								
32								
34								
35								
36								
40								
41								

Figure 7: Enter results in automatic referencing.

Step 5. Populate data

Step 5.1

It is time to fill all the data using dragging. Let us work on the 'membership type column' for this example. Repeat the cell referencing step 4 to get first cell filled from the 'Raw' data and now drag the bottom-right corner (the small black square) of the cell containing the formula downwards. As you drag, Excel will automatically copy the formula to the cells below, adjusting the cell reference for each row to match the corresponding data in the "Raw" sheet. This efficiently populates all the required rows with the formula as shown in Figure 8.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Income bracket(not currently in use)							
	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector	Gender (not currently in use)	Income bracket(not currently in use)	Postcode
4	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw		Core					
5			Plus					
7			Premium					
8			Core					
9			Student					
13			Core					
14			Plus					
16			Premium					
17			Core					
18			Student					
22			Core					
23			Plus					
25			Premium					
26			Core					
27			Student					
31			Core					
32			Plus					
34			Premium					
35			Core					
36			Student					
40			Core					
41			Plus					

Figure 8: Populate one column by dragging.

Step 5.2: Alternate method

Hold down the shift key and press the down arrow key repeatedly to select all the rows you want to populate with the formula. Alternatively, you can use the mouse to drag and select the desired range of cells. Next, press Ctrl + D on your keyboard. This will copy the formula you just entered in the first cell to all the selected cells, adjusting the cell reference for each row as needed.

Tip: Autofill can be faster for large datasets, while keyboard shortcuts might offer more control for smaller selections.

Step 5.3

Use one of the methods from step 5 i.e., autofill or keyboard shortcuts to populate the formula for the first desired column in the "Data Cleaning" sheet.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector	Gender (not currently in use)	Income bracket(not currently in use)	Postcode	Joined Date	Expiration Date
4	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practitioners	do not prefer to share	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
5	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	male	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
7	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Design, Performing Arts, Theatre, Visual Arts, Education	female	40k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
8	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice	female	more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
9	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F8 L8	Core	Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy	male	10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
13	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practitioners	do not prefer to share	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
14	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	female	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
16	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Design, Performing Arts, Theatre, Visual Arts, Education	female	40k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
17	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice	female	more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
18	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F8 L8	Core	Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy	female	10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
22	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practitioners	female	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
23	mf95XdLid22LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	male	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	2028-02-08

Figure 9: Populated data for further analysis.

Data analysis

Step 6. Create a data analysis sheet

Repeat Step 2 here and name the sheet as “Data analysis”. You can use this sheet to perform various analytical tasks required for the organisation to learn trends and link data to create meaningful connections and results. This sheet will serve as a single source for all the analysis in one place.

13										
14										
15										
16										
17										
18										
19										
20										
21										
22										
23										
24										
25										
26										

Figure 10: Data analysis sheet.

Step 7. Identify data

In your "Data Cleaning" sheet, highlight all the relevant data you want to analyse using the pivot table. This step is just for knowing what to analyse. This should include columns containing information like "Gender," "Income" (assuming it's numerical), and any other relevant data points like "Creative sector" you want to explore as shown in the figure below.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector	Gender (not currently in use)	Income bracket(not currently in use)	Postcode	Joined Date	Expiration Date
4	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners	do not prefer to share	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
5	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	male	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
7	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Design, Performing Arts, Theatre, Visual Arts, Education	female	40k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
8	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice	female	more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
9	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F8 L8	Core	Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy	male	10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
13	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners	do not prefer to share	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
14	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	female	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
16	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Design, Performing Arts, Theatre, Visual Arts, Education	female	40k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
17	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice	female	more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	2028-02-08
18	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F8 L8	Core	Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy	female	10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
22	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners	female	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	2028-02-08
23	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	male	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	2028-02-08

Figure 11: Identify your data range

Step 8. Pivot table

Step 8.1

Navigate to the top menu bar in Google sheets and click on the "Insert" option. From the dropdown menu, select "Pivot table."

Figure 3: Locate pivot table

A pop-up window titled "Create pivot table" will appear. Select 'new sheet' as we want do not want to clutter the 'data cleaning' sheet. This creates a new sheet dedicated to your pivot table. Select this option to keep your data and pivot table separate.

Step 8.2

As the columns were identified in step 7, we will have to select a data range to create table.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1									
	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector	Gender (not currently in use)	Income bracket(not currently in use)	Postcode	Joined Date
4	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners	do not prefer to share	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15
5	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	do not prefer to share	more than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12
7	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Direct Artistic Services	do not prefer to share	10k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12
8	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice	do not prefer to share	more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12
9	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F8 L8		Core Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy	female	10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15
13	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners	female	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15
14	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	do not prefer to share	more than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12
16	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Direct Artistic Services	do not prefer to share	10k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12
17	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice	do not prefer to share	more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12
18	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F8 L8		Core Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy	female	10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15
22	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners	female	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15
23	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	male	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12

Figure 4: Data range.

And be more specific as shown below:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1										
	Unique ID	Full Name	Membership Type	Status	Creative Sector		Income bracket(not currently in use)	Postcode	Joined Date	Expiration Date
4	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners		10k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	
5	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing		more than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	
7	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Direct Artistic Services		10k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	
8	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice		more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	
9	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F8 L8		Core Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy		10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15	
13	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners		10k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	
14	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing		more than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	
16	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F6 L6	Student	Self-Employed	Direct Artistic Services		10k-50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	
17	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F7 L7	Business	Employed	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice	female	more than 50k	EH4 7OK	2019-02-12	
18	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F8 L8		Core Self-Employed	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy	female	10k-20k	EH4 7OK	2021-02-15	
22	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F3 L3	Student	Self-Employed	Creative Practioners	female	20k-30k	EH9 5UY	2021-02-15	
23	mf95XdLidZ2LW2ikw	F4 L4	Premium	Self-Employed	Advertising and Marketing	male	less than 5k	EH9 5UY	2019-02-12	

Figure 5: Specific data range.

Step 9. Pivot table layout

Name this new sheet as "Pivot table". The left section is blank. The middle section houses the pivot table editor controls. The right section displays the actual pivot table with rows, columns, and values based on your chosen fields and configuration.

Tip: You can adjust the width of each section (blank, editor, pivot table) by dragging the borders between them. This can help you customise the viewing experience based on your needs.

Figure 6: Pivot table layout.

Step 10. Learn to drag required fields

As an example, drag "Creative Sector" to Columns: This will group your data by different creative fields.

Figure 7: Creative sector as columns.

Step 11. Populate the editor

The configuration here in this example editor is putting "Gender" in rows, "Income Brackets" in the filter, and "Creative Sector" in columns can be a great starting point for analysing your membership data. One example could be to select suggested method to count the gender in each creative sector as show below in Figure 18.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	COUNTA of Gender (not currently in use)	Gender (not currently in use)				
2	Creative Sector	do not prefer to share	female	male	Grand Total	
3				9	9	
4	Advertising and Marketing			2	3	5
5	Creative Practioners	3	2			5
6	Design, Digital Media, Film & Video, Performing Arts, Photography, Theatre			5		5
7	Design, Performing Arts, Theatre, Visual Arts, Education			5		5
8	Multi-Disciplinary and Participatory Practice			5		5
9	Publishing				5	5
10	Services Supporting Creatives and Consultancy			2	3	5
11	Grand Total	3	30	11	44	

Figure 8: Creative sector and gender relationship.

Step 12. Other examples

Continuing from step 11, Click on the dropdown arrow next to "Income Brackets". This will expand the filter options.

filter the income in 10k-20k and the table shows how many genders are in a particular sector and what are their incomes. Look for the income range of 10k-20k within the filter options and click the checkbox next to "10k-20k" to select this income range. Once you've applied the income filter, the pivot table in the centre section of your sheet will update to reflect only members within the 10k-20k income range.

Figure 9: Creative Sector composition for members in the 10k-20k Income Bracket.

This analysis may answer some crucial questions like: Income Distribution: How is income distributed across different creative sectors for each gender? Are there any significant differences? Gender Differences: For each creative sector, are there differences in average income between genders? Target Market: Can you identify specific creative sectors or income segments that might be of particular interest for marketing efforts?

By following these steps and creatively using pivot tables, one can gain valuable insights into the relationship between different variables like gender, creative sector, and income within your membership base. This knowledge can inform strategies for member engagement, targeted marketing campaigns, and potentially customising membership offerings to cater to different member segments and securing buy in for government funding.

This step-by-step guide can transform raw data from your membership platform into actionable insights. You can learn about trends in member behaviour, identify groups with specific characteristics, and understand the connections between various factors that influence membership engagement or other relevant metrics.

This knowledge can empower your organisation to make data-driven decisions that improve member experience and achieve overall organisation's goals along with empowering people.

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